

Electron Beam Lithography of sensitive resist based on photoacid generator integrated terpolymer: potentiality of high-resolution pattern transfer

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Nanolithography technology has been extensively used in semiconductor fabrication process to manufacture micro/nano electronics. Now a days developing new photoresist materials for different lithography applications in successful pattern transfer has been the key role in semiconductor industries for next-generation IC technology node. On these note, we have designed and synthesized a new terpolymer viz. GBLMA-MAMA-MAPDST photoresists for the electron beam lithography (EBL) applications (1, 2). EBL studies reveal that the synthesized terpolymer resist (GBLMA-MAMA-MAPDST) is sensitive to the e-beam with 100 nm (L/S) and 70 nm isolated positive tone line features after TMAH development. The terpolymer resist showed remarkable sensitivity (E_0) and contrast ratio (γ) of $\sim 36.5 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and ~ 0.08 , respectively. Eventually, the potential to transfer positive higher resolution nano-features on the silicon substrate has been demonstrated by suitable dry plasma etching technique.

Fig. 1. (a) Structure of Terpolymer, (b) EBL pattern of 100 nm L/S, (c) AFM image of transferred pattern onto Silicon.

Keywords: EBL, Integrated Terpolymer, Pattern Transfer, Sensitive Resist.

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